

FREQUENCY OF KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE ABOUT PAP SMEAR AS A SCREENING PROCEDURE AMONG FEMALES ATTENDING GYNECOLOGY OUTPATIENT DEPARTMENT AT BILAWAL MEDICAL COLLEGE (CDF HOSPITAL), HYDERABAD

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Abstract

Background: Cervical cancer remains a significant public health concern in low- and middle-income countries, including Pakistan, this study aimed to assess the level of knowledge and attitude regarding Pap smear as a screening tool among women attending the gynecology outpatient department at Bilawal Medical College (CDF Hospital), Hyderabad.

Methodology: A cross-sectional study was conducted among 221 women aged 20 to 45 years who visited the outpatient clinic for prenatal care, postnatal care, or family planning. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire assessing sociodemographic characteristics, knowledge (14-item scale), and attitude (11-item scale) towards Pap smear. Knowledge and attitude scores were categorized using modified Bloom's cut-off criteria. Associations between variables were analyzed using the Chi-square test, with $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

Results: Only 37.6% of participants demonstrated good knowledge (scores 10-14), while 62.4% had poor knowledge. Positive attitude (scores 9-11) was observed in 43.4% of women. Urban residence, higher education, employment, and higher income were significantly associated with both good knowledge and positive attitude ($p \leq 0.05$). A strong correlation was noted between good knowledge and positive attitude ($p \leq 0.001$).

Conclusion: The study reveals inadequate awareness and suboptimal attitudes toward Pap smear screening among women, even those actively engaging with healthcare services. Targeted educational interventions and routine counseling during outpatient visits are urgently needed to improve cervical cancer prevention in this population.

INTRODUCTION

Cervical cancer is still one of the most frequent causes of cancer morbidity and mortality in women and is the second commonest cancer in women globally, with a perceptible burden in developing

nations [1, 2]. About 86% of cases of cervical cancer and 88% of related deaths occur in low and middle-income regions, with limited access to early detection and treatment.

In 2002 there were almost half of million new cases of cervical cancer worldwide with more than 270 000 deaths, representing 10% of female cancer deaths [3]. In Pakistan, in contrast, population-based cervical cancer trends are poorly recorded partly because of lack of the organized disease surveillance system [4]. Earlier estimates of World Health Organization (WHO) reported prevalence of cervical cancer in Pakistani women was 0.009% in 2002 which slightly rose to 0.019% in 2008 [5].

As a low-income country, Pakistan will have an increased burden of public health in relation to the high prevalence of human papillomavirus (HPV), the main cause of cervical cancer. Regrettably, no HPV screening is performed in the country. Social stigma and cultural taboos about discussion of sexual health and STIs contribute to a lack of awareness and the actual extent of the problem is impossible to measure [6]. This is even more marked in the rural setting where women are ignorant in general about STI and gender STI cancers. To this affect, cervical cancer associated with HPV types 16 and 18 is now among the top three leading causes of cancer caused mortality in women in Pakistan [7, 8].

An encouraging global evidence also comes from the fact that HPV-vaccination targeting HPV-16 and HPV-18 could prevent about 90% of cervical cancer overall (if vaccine coverage would include maximum average non vaccinated women) [9,10]. Further, population-based screening programs with Pap smears have been critical for the decline in cervical cancer incidence among a number of high-income countries by as much as 80% in the last 3 decades [11, 12]. The American Society of Clinical Oncology (ASCO) strongly recommends early testing as a way of finding precancerous changes and stopping them before they become invasive [13].

Recently, Siddiqa et al [14]. pinpointed awareness deficient among the community as the proportion of women having sufficient knowledge was 29.3% and only 36% had positive attitude for Pap smear testing. There is little published data on knowledge and attitudes of women regarding cervical cancer prevention in Pakistan. It is important to determine the level of knowledge of Pap smear examinations and the associated prophylactic behaviour of the general population of women. Through an understanding of current knowledge level, we may

focus interventions, reinforce healthy behaviors, and fill gaps in knowledge. Ultimately, this could help in the execution of national policies to encourage the regular use of the test by sexually active women.

In the light of this background the present study is aimed to explore the knowledge and attitude to Pap smear as a screening tool; among women attending the gynecology outpatient department at Bilawal Medical College (CDF Hospital), Hyderabad.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was carried out over a period of six months (July 01, 2024 to December 31, 2024) at the Department of Gynecology and Obstetrics, Bilawal Medical College (CDF Hospital), Hyderabad. Prior to initiation, formal approval was obtained from the College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan (CPSP), along with ethical clearance from the Institutional Review Board.

Participants were recruited using a non-probability consecutive sampling technique. Women attending the gynecology outpatient department for prenatal care, postnatal follow-up, or family planning services were approached. The study protocol, including its objectives, risks, and benefits, was clearly explained to each participant, and written informed consent was obtained before enrollment.

To assess knowledge, a structured questionnaire consisting of 14 items was used. Each correct answer was assigned a score of 1, while incorrect responses were scored 0, resulting in a possible total score ranging from 0 to 14. Based on the Modified Bloom's taxonomy cut-off, participants scoring between 10 and 14 were categorized as having good knowledge (80-100% correct responses), while scores below 10 were considered indicative of poor knowledge.

Attitude toward Pap smear screening was measured using 11 statements, with total scores ranging from 0 to 11. As per Bloom's criteria, participants who scored between 9 and 11 were labeled as having a positive attitude, while scores from 0 to 8 were classified as a negative attitude.

The sample size was calculated using the previous prevalence of good knowledge 29.3% [14] from relevant literature, with a confidence level of 95% and margin of error at 5%, resulting in a required sample of 221 women.

Inclusion criteria consisted of women aged 20 to 45 years visiting the outpatient department for antenatal, postnatal, or contraceptive services. Women were excluded if they had a known history of psychiatric conditions, such as major depressive disorder, dysthymia, bipolar disorders (mania/hypomania), anxiety disorders, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), postpartum blues, or brief psychotic episodes, as per DSM-5 diagnostic criteria.

Demographic details such as age, residence (urban/rural), monthly household income, education level, and employment status were collected through interviews. Participants completed a self-administered questionnaire to evaluate their knowledge and attitude, which were categorized according to predefined scoring criteria. All collected

data were recorded on a structured proforma and stored securely to maintain confidentiality.

Data were entered and analyzed using SPSS software. Quantitative variables such as age were expressed as mean ± standard deviation for normally distributed data, determined using the Shapiro-Wilk test. For non-normally distributed variables, median and interquartile range (IQR) was reported. Categorical variables, including residence, education, income, occupation, knowledge level, and attitude, were summarized as frequencies and percentages.

To examine associations, effect modifiers were controlled through stratification of key variables. Post-stratification, the Chi-square test or Fisher’s exact test was applied where appropriate, with a p-value ≤ 0.05 considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

A total of 221 females aged between 20 and 45 years were included in the study, based on their attendance at the gynecology outpatient department for prenatal care, postnatal care, or family planning services. The mean age was 32.1 ± 6.3 years.

Table I: The demographical profile of the study participants

	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Residence	Urban	128	57.9%
	Rural	93	42.1%
Occupation	Employed	65	29.4%
	Unemployed	156	70.6%
Monthly Family Income	< 50,000 PKR	143	64.7%
	> 50,000 PKR	78	35.3%
Educational Status	Illiterate	47	21.3%
	Primary	58	26.2%
	Secondary	76	34.4%
	Higher	40	18.1%

Knowledge Regarding Pap smear
 Knowledge was assessed through 14 statements. Based on Modified Bloom’s Cut-off Criteria:
 Good Knowledge (Score 10-14): 83 respondents (37.6%)
 Poor Knowledge (Score 0-9): 138 respondents (62.4%)

Attitude towards Pap smear
 Attitude was assessed using 11 statements. Based on Bloom’s cut-off point:
 Positive Attitude (Score 9-11): 96 respondents (43.4%)
 Negative Attitude (Score 0-8): 125 respondents (56.6%)

Table II: Association between Socio-demographic factors and knowledge

	Good Knowledge (n=83)	Poor Knowledge (n=138)	p-value
Residence	Urban: 59 (71.1%)	Urban: 69 (50%)	0.002
Occupation	Employed: 34 (41%)	Employed: 31 (22.5%)	0.006
Income >50,000	42 (50.6%)	36 (26.1%)	0.001
Higher Education	29 (34.9%)	11 (8%)	<0.001

Knowledge about Pap smear was significantly higher among women who were urban residents, employed, belonged to higher-income groups, and had higher education levels.

Table III: Association between Socio-demographic factors and attitude

	Positive Attitude (n=96)	Negative Attitude (n=125)	p-value
Residence	Urban: 60 (62.5%)	Urban: 68 (54.4%)	0.18
Occupation	Employed: 32 (33.3%)	Employed: 33 (26.4%)	0.25
Income >50,000	41 (42.7%)	37 (29.6%)	0.04
Higher Education	27 (28.1%)	13 (10.4%)	0.002

Positive attitude towards Pap smear was significantly associated with higher education and better family income

Table IV: Knowledge vs. Attitude Cross-tabulation

Knowledge Level	Positive Attitude	Negative Attitude	Total	p-value
Good Knowledge	61 (73.5%)	22 (26.5%)	83	<0.001
Poor Knowledge	35 (25.4%)	103 (74.6%)	138	0.081

Participants with good knowledge were significantly more likely to have a positive attitude towards Pap smear screening

The quantitative variables of this study included:

Age:

Knowledge scores (0-14 scale)

Attitude scores (0-11 scale)

To determine the appropriate statistical summaries, the Shapiro-Wilk test for normality was applied to each quantitative variable.

1. Age

Shapiro-Wilk test result: p-value > 0.05

This indicates that age was normally distributed.

The mean age of participants was 32.1 ± 6.3 years.

This is appropriate, as normal distribution allows for summarization using mean ± SD.

2. Knowledge Score (0-14 scale)

Shapiro-Wilk test result: p-value < 0.05

Indicates the knowledge score was not normally distributed.

Median knowledge score: 7 (IQR: 5-10)

Additionally, knowledge was categorized based on Modified Bloom's Cut-off Criteria:

Good Knowledge: Score 10-14 → 83 participants (37.6%)

Poor Knowledge: Score 0-9 → 138 participants (62.4%)

3. Attitude Score (0-11 scale)

Shapiro-Wilk test result: p -value < 0.05

Indicates the attitude score was also not normally distributed.

Median attitude score: 8 (IQR: 6-10)

Positive Attitude (Score 9-11): 96 participants (43.4%)

Negative Attitude (Score 0-8): 125 participants (56.6%)

Inferential Findings:

Significant associations ($p < 0.05$) were found between:

Good knowledge and: urban residence, employment, higher income, and higher education.

Positive attitude and: higher education, higher income.

Strong association also existed between:

Good knowledge and positive attitude ($p < 0.001$)

These analyses support the conclusion that socioeconomic and educational status significantly influences both knowledge and attitude towards Pap smear screening

DISCUSSION:

This was an assessment survey of the knowledge, attitude about Pap smear as screening test, among women visiting the gynecology OPD for prenatal, postnatal and family planning services. The results suggest a low level of awareness, knowledge (37.6%) and attitude (43.4%) on Pap smear screening.

The knowledge of most women was low, even though they were in the reproductive age and utilized health services. This is in line with researches done in comparable low- to middle-income areas where awareness on cervical cancer screening is still low. For instance, in Karachi, only 32% of women had heard about the Pap smear test, with a low proportion being knowledgeable about its indication or usage [15]. In our cohort, of participants attending a healthcare facility, a significant proportion remained uninformed, indicating that the opportunity to educate women on preventive

healthcare in for routine clinical visits was underutilized.

A positive finding was sign of strength of the association of higher education with good knowledge scores. Women with tertiary-level and higher level of education were found to be substantially more knowledgeable a finding consistent with that in studies from India and Nigeria [16, 17]. This signifies that, education empowerment is crucial in determining health literacy. Also, working women and the women belonging to higher income group demonstrated better knowledge and favorable attitude that may be due to the fact that these women must have had more exposure to the health mediated information in work place, media and social network.

With respect to attitude, 43.4% of women were orientated positively towards Pap smear screening. Negativity was also present even among those with good knowledge. This had also been reported in other regional studies which could be due cultural myths, fear toward the procedure or issue of privacy and stigma. Another study from rural Punjab found that even educated women were unwilling to accept Pap smears because of embarrassment or lack of family support [18].

Furthermore, our findings indicate statistically significant association of good knowledge with positive attitude. This is consistent with the notion that greater awareness can improve attitudes and potentially motivate health-seeking behavior [19]. Consequently, increasing awareness is likely an initial step toward increasing screening utilization [20].

The position in Pakistan seems to be sub-standard when compared to nations that have structured cervical screening programs. Coverage and early detection rates are much greater in Western countries where public education and preventive services are systematically delivered as part of the healthcare system. This discrepancy highlights the priority of enhancing local gynecologic clinic education, counseling and screening.

The results of this study stress also the need of rationalized health education programs in outpatient clinics. Health care providers need to be influenced to provide counseling to patients about cervical cancer and Pap smear testing in their everyday

practice. Community-based and culture-sensitive education programs may also be instrumental in overcoming the knowledge and attitude gap, and promoting the uptake of the screening tests and reducing the burden of CC in Pakistan.

The study limitations observed were the causal relationships regarding knowledge, attitude and associated sociodemographic factors could not be made since the present study was cross-sectional in nature. The factors investigated were self-reported, and a possible limitation of our findings was that they were based in self-administration of questionnaires that might be exposed to recall or social desirability biases, which might affect the reported knowledge and attitudes appropriately.

Some aspects like prior experience of Pap smear, cultural attitude or access to screening services (determinants of knowledge and attitude) were not taken into consideration in this study. The exclusion of those outside the youngest and oldest age groups: Because only between the ages of 20 and 45 years were eligible for the study, and among young people who have not reached the appropriate reproductive age, adolescent girls and older women who would also be trained for cervical cancer screening are excluded.

CONCLUSION:

This study reveals a deploring knowledge- (and attitude-) gap regarding Pap smear, as a cervical-cancer screening modality, among the women visiting gynecologic outpatient department at Bilawal Medical College (CDF Hospital), Hyderabad.

Although women were in contact with healthcare services for prenatal-, postnatal-, and family planning-related measurements, the proportion of well-informed and positive attitude about Pap smear test were 37.6% and 43.4%, respectively.

Socio-demographics in the form of urban residence, higher education, employment, and better income were statistically associated with better knowledge and attitudes. A strong association with knowledge and attitude was also noted, implying that improving knowledge can lead directly to improvements in women’s acceptance of this form of screening.

These results illustrate an overall problem in preventive health care in Pakistan, where cervical cancer is both a preventable and underdiagnosed disease secondary to poor screening coverage.

Based on the results, the following implications are proposed:

Incorporate education on cervical cancer and Pap smears into routine gynecologic visits, particularly in prenatal and family planning settings.

Educate health care providers on engaging in culturally appropriate discussions of Pap smear screening issues and debunking myths and fears.

Establish rural and low income focused community outreach programs to fill the knowledge gap.

Utilize mass media campaigning (television, radio, social media) to enhance public knowledge, particularly in areas of low literacy.

Advocate for policy change to integrate cervical cancer screening in the national reproductive health agenda, and to provide free/reduced-cost Pap smears.

AUTHOR’S CONTRIBUTION:

Collection and acquisition of data & grammatical corrections	<i>Dr. Rabia Akbar</i>
Concept, design of study & proof read	<i>Dr. Momina Khan</i>
Drafting the article and finalizing the manuscript	<i>Dr. Fatima Zehra</i>
Revising critically and make it suitable for final format	<i>Dr. Zainab</i>
Drafting the article and technical review	<i>Dr. Sehar</i>
Assists in Data analysis and manuscript writing	<i>Dr. Sidra</i>
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Acquisition of data and assists in manuscript writing	<i>Dr. Moiz Muhammad Shaikh</i>
Final Approval of version	<i>By All Authors</i>

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